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Europe's deportation regime: Key actors, structural interdependencies, and dominant discourses on enforced return

Introduction

This literature review serves to map the position of and approach to enforced return from the perspective of various actors operating in Europe's deportation regime. We use *enforced return* as an umbrella term that includes assisted and incentivized "voluntary" return as well as forced removals from nation state's territories.¹ While at the beginning of the twentieth century, the enforced return of unlawfully residing residents was commonly considered unacceptable, it became 'utterly banal' at the end of the same century (De Genova & Peutz 2010). Ever since, social scientists have documented the rise of what Gibney (2008) calls "the deportation state", showing that enforced return became an increasingly normalized tool for states in their efforts to curb and control migration. Despite its widespread usage, significant empirical evidence points to the existence of a "deportation gap" (ibid): a substantial mismatch between the number of removal orders issued and those actually enforced. In their attempts to close this purported gap, states in the Global North therefore take a myriad of measures to increase enforced returns. These include persuading illegalized migrants² to return "voluntarily" (Cleton & Chauvin 2020) through so-called Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR) programs, which are operated by international organizations like the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), but also increasing their resources and capacity to deport (Leerkes & van Houte 2020) and by seeking to elicit the cooperation of migrants' countries of citizenship through signing EU-wide and bilateral readmission agreements and other (non-binding) arrangements (Cassarino 2010). These readmission agreements are more-or-less formal appointments made in bilateral or multilateral settings, that regulate this process of enforced return (Trauner 2018).

In seeking to make sense of their relationships, power imbalances between actors and their everyday practices, De Genova and Peutz (2010) introduced the concept of the "deportation regime". For them, it serves as a common denominator for a global regime that implicates relationships between deporting and receiving states, international organizations, and non-governmental organizations in setting up and sustaining the framework for governing populations worldwide. This paper provides a non-exhaustive review of the academic literature on actors that operate within the European deportation regime specifically. Following the academic literature on migration regimes, we center the converging and diverging positions of various actors embedded in this deportation regime, including international organizations, the European Union, various EU+ states core to the Finding Agreement in Return (FAiR) project and NGOs. We decided to focus our work on these institutional actors due to their involvement in return policy making and implementation in Europe. By doing this, however, we omit three important actors in this paper: illegalized migrants, their countries of citizenship, as well as

¹ When applicable, this also covers returns from the external borders of the EU, or so-called pushbacks. Especially for particular countries at EU's external border, such as Poland, enforced return dynamics from their territory are difficult to understand without also detailing the workings of return at the border.

² Throughout the working paper, we use the term 'illegalized' to highlight the institutional and political processes that render certain immigrants as 'illegal'.

European Agencies like Frontex who assume an increasingly important role in enforced return (Previatello 2023). Without downplaying their role in shaping the deportation regime, we will further deepen their role in different deliverables as part of the project.

Conceptually, this review draws on the interdisciplinary literature on “regimes” in the social sciences. “Regime” is not a unified concept and entered the social sciences at large, and migration research specifically, via different routes. The first and most influential regime approach was introduced by scholars of international relations in the 1970s. Here, regimes are commonly seen as "networks of rules, norms, and procedures that regularize behavior and control its effects" (Krasner 1983, also in Keohane and Nye 1977). Following their lead, Gosh (2000) was among the first to call for the introduction of an “international migration regime” in the wider field of migration studies, arguing that it would lead to a harmonization of management practices and rationales. Krasner (1983, 3) indeed emphasized that within a regime, actors eventually converge their expectations and actions within a given issue area. Political scientists and scholars of international relations have however emphasized that international migration defies this ordering principle since it is linked to a wide variety of distinct issue areas which partially follow different logics (Lahav & Lavenex 2012). Instead, a multitude of international norms and cooperation agreements have emerged that together form what has been called the "international migration regime complex" (Betts 2009, Kunz 2011). This regime complex consists of a multilayered system of governance structures that combines different forms of cooperation and sometimes leads to actors and interests competing with one another. Regime analysis has also been deployed in migration studies by critical border scholars (Tsianos & Hess 2012, Mezzadra & Neilson 2013), following the French regulation school. These are manifested in critical examinations of regulatory practices in Europe's borderlands, by analytically centering actors' practices of control, contestation and subversion that are related to wider relations of power, domination, and inequality. Finally, migration scholars who deploy Foucaultian governmentality vocabulary also adopt a regime-theoretical approach: they shift attention to political rationalities that inform technologies used for the governance of mobility (Horvath et al. 2017).

For purposes of this review, we take from this work on regimes a sensibility to the interrelated practices, politics, and rationalities of enforced return. Whereas each strand of “regime analysis” detailed above has its own emphasis, they converge in at least two important ways. First, Horvath and colleagues (2017) detail that regime analyses emphasize the complexity and contradictions in political formations and governing practices. Migration control is conceived as the fitting together of different elements, including actors, practices, technologies and discourses that together co-produce the regime as polycentric, multidirectional and fluid. Regime analysis understands actors in various, heterogeneous subject positions that are not necessarily organized oppositional, nor consistent over time (Eule et al. 2019, Tsianos & Hess 2012). Leerkes and van Houte (2020) also highlighted this inherent multiplicity of Europe's deportation regime, emphasizing the differences in enforcement strategies and capacities between regions and countries. In our review below, we likewise highlight the convolution of different actors operating enforced return and readmission in Europe, who work in a multi-level governance system, yet do not always align in their aims and goals. Second, as alluded to above, regime analyses highlight the importance of norms and discourses in the regulation of migration, borders, and return. Below, we will emphasize the role of different actors as producers of particular norms and discourses on enforced return and dissect how these couple with wider rationalities on humanitarianism, securitization, utility, and human rights.

In surveying the literature on these actors' positions on return and readmission below, this working paper thus sheds light on 1) the multiplicity of actors, complementarities and complexities in enforced

return and readmission, and 2) the prevalent norms and discourses that inform the work of these actors and are produced by them. Following the multi-level governance structure of enforced return and readmission, we will first review the literature on international organizations at the multilateral level, before moving on to the regional level of the EU and its member states. We end with a review of the literature on non-governmental organizations and their involvement in AVR. We will conclude by reflecting on the aforementioned themes of complementarities and complexity, as well as discourse and norms.

The roles of international organizations in enforced return

Over the past few decades, international organizations have taken a key role in Europe's deportation regime. The International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR) have thereby become particularly important partners in international cooperation on return and readmission by shaping and spreading return policies, enabling readmission agreements, and implementing return programs.

Only towards the end of the past century and against the backdrop of a proliferation of international organizations, have scholars turned them into objects of academic scrutiny, recognizing their role and relevance in world politics. Thereby, researchers have mostly shed light on the reasons behind their emergence, unveiled their characteristics and power, or pointed to their potential dysfunctions (e.g., Abbott & Snidal 1998, Barnett & Finnemore 1999, Geiger & Pécoud 2010). From the perspective of states, international organizations have become particularly popular as they can serve state interests by reducing transaction costs, providing public goods, producing expert knowledge, promoting international norms and standards, and potentially also spreading their worldviews (Abbott & Snidal, 1998). The proliferation of international organizations provides states also with a large variety of alternative venues for policy-making, allowing them to disengage with existing forms and forums of international cooperation (Pevehouse & von Borzyskowski 2016). Ironically, the power of international organizations in world politics is built on their bureaucratic characteristics and their "appearance of depoliticization" (ibid., p. 708). Mimicking a technocratic approach to migration, international organizations have become notorious for using the notion of *migration management* to both describe their modus operandi and justify their mandate and actions (Geiger & Pécoud 2010).

In the field of international migration, international organizations are exercising a wide array of functions at the national, regional, and global level. Besides taking a role in the policy-making and the implementation process they are shaping the categories and discourses on migration. In Europe's deportation regime, IOM and UNHCR have become key actors in the implementation of EU migration governance and the diffusion of EU migration policies (Lavenex 2016). At the state level, they are likewise providing expert knowledge, advocating for particular policies and practices, or even implementing or acting as substituting state functions (Geiger & Pécoud 2010). The institutional proliferation of organizations, networks, and forums in the field of international migration has provided states with a large array of possibilities for international cooperation (Betts 2009).

To fulfil their mandate, international organizations such as the UNHCR and IOM depend on voluntary donations by states as well as non-state organizations and private actors. Over the past few decades,

UNHCR and IOM have succeeded to substantially increase their budget and diversify their portfolio of donors. Nevertheless, both organizations still heavily depend on the donations of a handful of donor states that are located in the Global North (Roper & Barria 2010, Patz & Thorvaldsdottir 2020). The voluntariness and the fact that many of these donations are earmarked renders the organizations particularly vulnerable to the interests of these donor states (Graham 2015, 2017). Against this background, the increasing engagement in the issue of return migration could be viewed as an attempt by these organizations to please the interest of main donor states. However, recent research also indicates that at least UNHCR has proven substantial autonomy in the implementation of its mandate (Thorvaldsdottir et al. 2022). UNHCR's engagement in return and readmission has sparked some conflicts with IOM but has also led to new forms of cooperation between both organizations (Elie 2010, Koch 2014).

The role of IOM

When IOM was founded in 1951, it was known under the name Provisional Intergovernmental Committee for the Movement of Migrants from Europe (PICMME), then renamed as the Intergovernmental Committee for European Migration (ICEM), before it received its current name (Elie, 2010). IOM was established outside of the UN system as the United States wanted to exclude the communist countries from this organization that was initially primarily foreseen to resettle Europeans to overseas countries (ibid.). Nevertheless, the IOM has developed into a powerful and global player in the migration regime, with a stark increase in staff, budget, and activities (Betts 2009, Lebon-McGregor 2023). It has built up a reputation as an efficient and flexible organization that secured its influence by supporting states in the everyday practice of migration governance and engaging in crisis management (Bradley 2017).

In 2018, IOM has become—somewhat loosely—integrated into the formal UN architecture (Moretti 2021). IOM joined the UN as a result of a major shift based on which the organization increasingly adopted a human rights discourse and embraced humanitarian principles (Bradley & Erdilmen 2023). This policy shift was found to be motivated by the intensified collaboration with the UN in humanitarian operations, a stronger focus on human rights by the organization's top personnel as well as a response to the increasing emphasis on human rights norms in world politics (ibid.). Nevertheless, IOM's recent engagement in a human rights discourse and its integration in the UN system has also been criticized as a form of “blue-washing” and as an attempt to mask the inconsistency between the organizations humanitarian rhetoric and its engagement in migration control activities (Hirsch & Doig 2018, p. 684).

The IOM has been dubbed a “world organization” that has positioned itself at the intersection of state interests and human rights discourses, whilst promoting the neo-liberal promises of better migration management (Geiger & Koch 2018, p. 25). This strategic choice of an in-between position has proven to be highly useful for the IOM as it allows the organization to take up a wide array of activities in the global governance of migration, carrying out work for states and engaging profitably—whilst engaging in discourses on the rights of people on the move (Ashutosh & Mountz 2011). In light of its continuously expanding set of activities and given the difficulties in categorizing the IOM it has been characterized as an organization that is “neither fish nor fowl” (ibid., p. 22). However, the IOM has also been described as a “non-normative organization” as its main aim is neither to promote and defend migrants' rights in the first place nor to criticize the policies and practices of governments (Moretti 2021, p. 40).

The IOM's engagement in setting up programs of Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) dates back to the 1970s (Bartels 2017). In IOM's self-representation, its engagement and commitment to "voluntary" return is based on the organization's adherence to the principle of free movement of persons (Noll 1999). Even though some member states have contested this core principle of IOM, it has remained enshrined in article 2 of the IOM Constitution until today (IOM 2021). Consequently, it prevents the organization from engaging in the forceful return of people. Conversely, the principle has been essential for IOM to become the worldwide leading organization in the field of "voluntary" return (Bartels 2017). However, some scholars have argued that despite having built a worldwide reputation and network in return, the success of the AVRs has often been limited. More generally, migration scholars have questioned the voluntariness of "voluntary" returns that are central to IOM's engagement (Webber 2011, Kalir 2017, Leerkes et al. 2017, Cleton & Chauvin 2020). Pointing to the example of Morocco and Tunisia, Bartels (2020) claims that IOM programs have not led to an increasing rate of "voluntary" returns or a decrease in forced returns. Instead, these programs are considered to have primarily increased the number of return instruments and rendered the return regime more contested and less transparent (ibid.). IOM has also been engaged in promoting the return of internally displaced people, coordinating such repatriation processes in close cooperation with UNHCR (Gauci 2023).

To fully understand the role and relevance of IOM within the field of return and readmission one cannot simply consider IOM as an international actor that focuses on "voluntary" return from countries of destination to countries of origin only. For example, IOM gains an increasingly prominent role in "transit" countries, especially along the Mediterranean Route. An important part of this work is funded with EU money under the joint EU-IOM initiative. Launched in December 2016, so-called 'protection and assistance centers' have been established in Niger, Mali and Burkina Faso where illegalized migrants find temporary shelter and agree to a "voluntary humanitarian return scheme" back to their country of citizenship. These programs are contested by West African actors, partially because they are seen as an additional obstacle to completing migration processes but also because the promised reintegration support has not lived up to expectations (Trauner et al. 2019). Scholars therefore argue that IOM engages in "humanitarian borderwork" in countries such as Niger (Pallister-Wilkins 2017, p. 85) that is based on an approach that simultaneously "cares and controls" (Aradau 2004, Moreno-Lax 2018, p. 121). In doing so, the IOM strengthens the EU's border control and externalization mechanisms outside of Europe (de Blasis & Pitzalis, 2023).

Furthermore, one must also consider the organization's ambition within the field of readmission, its close cooperation with host states as well as its role within the return regime. While most of IOM's activities and programs on return are directly aiming to facilitate or process the return of people, the organization has also strived to foster return indirectly. For example, IOM aims to facilitate states to close bilateral readmission arrangements that include the possibility of "voluntary" return but often also include migration control measures (Ashutosh & Mountz 2011). More generally, the IOM's activities and cooperation with states were found to have served the aim of rendering people deportable (Bartels 2020). IOM has been viewed as contributing to the production of *deportability* of people within a complex interplay between state practices of repression, detention, and deportations based on coercive measures on the one hand as well as the provision of programs by IOM that promote the "voluntary" return of people that build on material incentives on the other hand (ibid.).

However, IOM has also played a decisive role in shaping discourses, defining categories, and framing issues in the field of return migration. In line with its in-between nature as an institution, IOM was also viewed to play a somewhat ambiguous role there. On the one hand, the organization has substantially

advocated for humanitarian issues and engaged in the human rights discourse (Bradley & Erdilmen 2023, Moretti 2021). On the other hand, however, IOM's engagement was found to be decisive in declaring Nigeria a "safe country" for return, leading to the enforcement of the return of rejected asylum seekers there (Creed et al. 2023). As an organizer and serving as secretariat for many inter-state consultation mechanisms that have proliferated in the past few decades, IOM has supported informal exchanges between states that are not only allowing the exchange of best practices and policies outside of the public eye but are also often aimed at increasing migration control and return (Betts 2009).

While the in-between position of IOM has brought the organization many advantages, it has also raised concerns and sparked criticism. For example, academics criticized a lack of accountability (Bradley et al. 2023), and an absence of a protection mandate (Pécoud 2018), and accused the organization of doing the dirty work of states (Abbott & Snidal 1998). As a consequence, IOM has been found to have become a complicit of repressive state practices or, put differently, states have instrumentalized the organization to legitimize their migration control mechanisms (Bartels, 2017). The criticism regarding the lack of independence is also based on the organization's donation structure which largely depends on the voluntary donations of states. Patz and Thorvaldsdottir (2020), for example, have shown that while IOM does not systematically respond to shifts in refugee numbers, the organization has been responsive to changes in donor interests. Against the background of the criticism of focusing more on the donor state's interest than on protecting people, the IOM adopted a protection policy in 2015 and struck an agreement with the UN that includes protection obligations in 2016 (Moretti, 2021). Besides formal commitment to human rights standards, it has stepped up its human rights discourse and its advocacy work for humanitarian standards (Bradley & Erdilmen 2023). Nevertheless, the ambiguous characteristics and positioning of IOM as well as open questions regarding the accountability of the organization persist until today.

The role of UNHCR

Since UNHCR's foundation in the 1950s, the promotion of refugee protection and the supervision of the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol have been at the center of the agency's role and mandate. The rights and interests of persons whose asylum application has been rejected and who do not qualify as refugees, by contrast, were initially viewed not to fall into UNHCR's competence. From the 1990s onwards, however, the refugee agency overcame its initial reluctance and was seeking a more active role in return and readmission (see e.g., UNHCR 1994, 1997, 2003, 2010). Consequently, the UNHCR has also been increasingly involved in return programs and operations. Examples include monitoring the situation of returnees from Southeast Asia to Vietnam under the Comprehensive Plan of Action in 1989 and the return of rejected asylum seekers from Switzerland to Sri Lanka in the mid-1990s (Noll 1999). By expanding its agenda to the issue of return (as well as other fields of migration governance), UNHCR had to strike an increasingly delicate balance between defending the rights of refugees and demonstrating responsiveness to the interests of states (Loescher 2001b).

During the Cold War, people fleeing from the communist East to the capitalist West, or vice versa, by crossing the Iron Curtain were viewed less as a threat than a sign confirming the superiority of their own political system (Gibney, 2004). For several decades, the return of people has therefore not been a priority for states and a non-issue for the UNHCR (Loescher 2001a). Yet, at the end of the Cold War, return increasingly became a possible outcome of asylum procedures. As a consequence, integration in the host country, protection in a third country, and return to the country of origin were all considered viable options by UNHCR (Barnett & Finnemore 1999). As states in Europe began to

stepwise limit access to asylum, the UNHCR advocated increasingly for “voluntary” repatriation (Takahashi 1997). Yet, as the issue moved steadily further up the agency’s agenda, the UNHCR focused more on the safety than the voluntariness of return and, in doing so, was found to legitimize the use of enforced return (Chimni 2004).

While the UNHCR has been reluctant at first to step into the field of return and readmission, the agency has continuously engaged in a large set of activities related to both fields over time. At the beginning of its engagement in return, UNHCR emphasized that it would only play a subsidiary role, referring to other international organizations such as IOM as well as national NGOs that were already active in the field (Noll 1999). By contrast, the UNHCR has been less hesitant to take a more active role in helping to close readmission agreements. Already in the 1990s, the UNHCR emphasized that it could enable and facilitate inter-state cooperation on an exceptional basis to this end (*ibid.*). Thereby, the UNHCR insisted on two criteria that must be respected for the agency to facilitate readmission agreements. First, UNHCR’s engagement must be in line with the mandate to protect refugees; second, its role in return should only be a supportive one as the main responsibility must remain in the hands of states (UNHCR 1997). Over time, the UNHCR engagement in inter-state dialogue became one of the key features of the agency (Koch 2014). The UNHCR’s increasing interest in readmission and the will to serve as a facilitator of inter-state cooperation could be based on the fact that UNHCR is heavily dependent on the state’s voluntary donations to the agency (Roper and Barria 2010). However, research on the influence of donor states is inconclusive and recent findings suggest that UNHCR has followed its mandate with substantial consistency (Thorvaldsdottir et al. 2022).

Continuously expanding its role in both inter-state cooperation facilitating readmission agreements and the monitoring of return operations, the UNHCR ultimately claimed responsibility for a wide array of activities. These included the preparation of return operations, the facilitation of inter-state cooperation in readmission, the assistance with reintegration, and the monitoring of returnees (UNHCR 2010). Besides taking an operational role in return, the UNHCR has also been involved in norm-building processes and thereby legitimized state-induced returns (Koch 2014). In a document of the Executive Committee, for example, the Committee recommends UNHCR to motivate states to take back their nationals and take a public position for the return of rejected asylum seekers to complement the efforts of states to return people that are found not to need protection (UNHCR 2003). In doing so, states are provided with the possibility of referring to the UNHCR’s positions and engagement to justify their return programs. The UNHCR justified its position on return as well as the broadening of its mandate by arguing that this engagement would be in line with its focus on protection as the return of rejected asylum seekers allows them to more effectively promote the rights of those who seek asylum or have been granted protection (Noll 1999).

Explaining the shift in the UNHCR’s position on return and readmission, researchers have stressed the changes in the international organization’s international environment (Geiger & Pécoud 2010, Koch 2014, Loescher 2001b). Betts (2009), for example, points to the increasing complexity of the refugee regime and its entanglement with other regimes that could render the UNHCR irrelevant if the agency would strictly stick to its narrow protection mandate. Furthermore, he claims that the increasing competition between international organizations and the proliferation of venues for refugee governance, force the UNHCR to make itself useful for states and take their interests into account (*ibid.*). Barnett and Finnemore (1999) foreground that the increasing focus on repatriation, instead of protection, could also be based on internal dynamics in the agency such as the increasingly technocratic approach of the agency, the limited consultation of refugees, and the will to strengthen cooperation with host and donor states.

The role of the EU

Since the beginning of European cooperation on migration and asylum, the deterrence of illegalized migration, including the return of unauthorized migrants, has been a priority. While resonating with migration policy discourses in influential member states, in particular France and Germany, this focus also followed functional demands arising from the choice to abolish controls at internal borders between the member states, codified in the 1985 and 1990 Schengen Agreements (Lavenex 2001a, 2001b). EU cooperation on asylum and immigration was henceforth framed as "compensatory measure" for the safeguarding of internal security in the internal borderless area, since the 1999 Amsterdam Treaty entitled "Area of Freedom, Security and Justice" (Lavenex 2018).

EU asylum and migration policy has thus been securitized early on (Huysmans 2000) and has from the start developed an external dimension towards countries of origin and transit of migrants and asylum-seekers (Lavenex 2006). This external dimension has fluctuated between more coercive and more partnership-oriented approaches (Boswell 2003). Throughout, and until today, the search for incentives to win these countries' cooperation has been a major concern for European actors (Lavenex 2023, Hoffmeyer et al. 2023).

Readmission, return and the "fight against illegal migration" were a core theme in the first proposals to harmonize member state's immigration policies by the Commission and the Council of Ministers (Coleman 2009, p. 19, Council of the EU 1991, p. 5). Already in 1993, the Justice and Home Affairs (JHA) Council discussed linking "Europe agreements, other association or co-operation agreements and third countries' practices as regards the readmission of illegal immigrants" (Council of the EU 1993, p. 6).

Starting in 1995, the EU Justice and Home Affairs Council adopted standard readmission clauses to be included in trade agreements on a case-by-case basis (Coleman 2009, p. 212). The clause was seen as a way to encourage the subsequent conclusion and implementation of bilateral readmission agreements between individual member states and the respective third countries. The 1999 Treaty of Amsterdam went along with a (shared) competence for the EU to conclude readmission agreements with third countries, reflecting the idea that acting at the EU level would generate more leverage towards partners that were perceived as uncooperative by the EU. The Council also adapted its position on the readmission clauses in EU agreements. It stated that such provisions should commit third countries to the conclusion of a dedicated EU readmission agreement and that this commitment should be included in all EU trade and broader association agreements as opposed to a case-by-case approach (Peers 2004, p. 219). One of the first moves of the member states under the Amsterdam Treaty was to give the Commission the mandate to negotiate readmission agreements with Morocco, Sri Lanka, Russia, and Pakistan (in 2000), with Hong Kong and Macao (in 2001) and with Ukraine, Albania, Algeria, Turkey, and China (in 2002, see Council of the European Union 2002a). Importantly, the mandate requested that such agreements would cover the obligation to readmit not only own nationals but also third-country nationals who were staying without legal status in the EU. As no corresponding obligation can be derived from international law, the negotiation of such readmission agreements turned out to be more challenging than expected. Already in 2002, the Commission had to admit that it faced considerable obstacles in obtaining such deals. It noted that since readmission agreements

"are solely in the interest of the Community, their successful conclusion depends very much on the "leverage" at the Commission's disposal. In that context it is important to note that, in the field of JHA, there is little that can be offered in return . . ." (European Commission 2002, p. 24).

It is in this context of searching for something to "be offered in return", i.e. positive conditionality, that the Commission and the member states started to look into possible linkages with other external policies. Soon, however, the member states invoked such linkages also for exerting negative conditionality or put differently, sanctioning non-cooperating third countries.

At the 2002 Seville European Council then Prime Ministers Blair and Aznar presented a joint initiative to make development aid and trade concessions conditional on third countries cooperating on migration control. This initiative meant that trade and development policy could be used to sanction countries that were perceived to be uncooperative by the EU. In doing so, the EU's approach would have shifted from one based on positive conditionality to one using negative conditionality. This initiative however was vividly objected by other member states.

The final Seville Council Conclusions thus implemented a softened form of the proposal. At least in terms of formal wording, the Council thus opted for an approach based on positive (incentives-based) rather than negative (sanctions-based) conditionality. It was agreed that each future EU association or cooperation agreement should include a clause on "joint management of migration flows and compulsory readmission in the event of illegal immigration" (European Council 2002), implying that the EU would no longer sign any association or cooperation agreement unless the other side agreed to the standard obligations regarding readmission and migration management. The Seville Conclusions also decided that "inadequate cooperation by a third state could hamper the establishment of closer relations between that country and the Union", following a systematic assessment of relations with that country (European Council 2002, p. 9).

Two years after Seville the 2004 General Affairs Council made the positive conditionality approach based on the offer of rewards explicit. It decided that a dedicated readmission agreement should become a precondition for the negotiation of a PTA: "on a case-by-case basis, a direct link should be established between the negotiation of cooperation, association or equivalent agreements and the conclusion of readmission agreements with the same third countries" (Coleman 2009, p. 197). Herewith, the use of conditionality was intensified as a dedicated and legally binding readmission agreement is a stronger instrument than a readmission clause included in a PTA (Coleman 2009, p. 219).

The difficulties encountered with the negotiation of readmission agreements led the member states to look to other sources of leverage, apart from trade agreements and negative conditionality, such as visa facilitations. The first countries to be offered this package deal were Russia and Ukraine, soon to be followed by the Western Balkan countries. Visa facilitation for tourist visits (i.e. not exceeding three months), which is what the EU has competence for, was no silver bullet, however. For instance, it did not suffice to convince the Southern Mediterranean neighbors such as Morocco or Tunisia to sign a readmission agreement (Cassarino 2007).

As a consequence, subsequent policy documents propagated a more comprehensive and softer approach in which migration control and readmission objectives are embedded in a wider set of "partnership" relations with target countries. Launched broadly at the same time as the partnership-oriented "European Neighborhood Policy", the 2005 Global Approach to Migration specified three areas for cooperation with third countries: cooperation on legal migration; the fight against illegalized migration; and the nexus between migration and development. In the wake of the Arab uprisings, this approach was reformed and the 2011 Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAMM) added a fourth area of cooperation: asylum and the protection of refugees.

From 2005 to 2015, the main instrument of the global approach has been the so-called Mobility Partnerships, non-legally binding memoranda of understanding aiming to improve cooperation in the four areas of the GAMM. Whereas the cooperation on migration was thus broadened within the context of the GAMM, the focus on illegalized migration remained a primary objective of the EU (Lavenex 2016, p. 6). In the early Mobility Partnerships signed with Cap Verde and central-east European countries the EU successfully required the prior signature of a formal readmission agreement before the conclusion of the partnership. This conditionality was later dropped however, and the Mobility Partnerships signed with Morocco (2013) and Tunisia (2014) merely convene the start of negotiations towards such an agreement (Lavenex & Stucky 2011, Reslow & Vink 2015). Around the same period, the "partnership" oriented approach also led to the conclusion of working arrangements providing for the third country's operational cooperation with the EU's external borders agency Frontex.

In reaction to the increasing politicization of migration in Europe as a result of the crisis of the European asylum system in 2015 the EU's reaction has been a reinvigoration of its search for powerful instruments of conditionality and an increased focus not only on readmission but also cooperation for externalizing border control (Lavenex 2018). According to the Commission the "ultimate aim" of the "Partnership Framework" adopted in 2016.

"is a coherent and tailored engagement where the Union and its Member States act in a coordinated manner putting together instruments, tools and *leverage* to reach comprehensive partnerships (compacts) with third countries to better manage migration. ...This means a change in approach and fresh thinking with a *mix of positive and negative incentives* and *the use of all leverages and tools*" (European Commission 2016, p. 6, emphasis added).

These package deals shall be concluded as "compacts" combining "different policy elements within EU competence (neighborhood policy, development aid, *trade*, mobility, energy, security, digital policy, etc.), leveraged towards the same objective" (European Commission 2016: 8, emphasis added). In parallel to this reinvigoration of the conditionality approach, external migration policy after 2016 is also marked by a pivot towards informal cooperation with third countries, sometimes exacerbating the limits of EU law. This includes the 2016 deal with Turkey, the cooperation with Libya, and the promotion of operational cooperation with third countries to return illegalized migrants and asylum seekers in a fast and informal manner such as in the "Joint Way Forward" with Afghanistan of 2016 (Lavenex 2018, Reslow 2019). The increased focus on countries along the main routes of unauthorized migration towards the EU and the informalization of cooperation (Cassarino 2007) suggests again a less important role for trade agreements in achieving cooperation since formal trade agreements require long processes of negotiation and are not easily changed once agreed.

A new turn in the conjuncture of conditionality and other approaches was launched in 2021 with the Commission's proposal to temporarily withdraw trade preferences under the EU's Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) towards countries that fail to readmit their own nationals. The Commission's proposal introduces two major changes to the EU's trajectory of return/readmission cooperation: Firstly, it shifts the EU's approach from one based on positive conditionality, that is, based on incentives, to one based on negative conditionality, i.e. the threat of sanctions. Secondly, it elevates a one-sided interest of the EU, readmission, at the same level as alleged global public goods hitherto subsumed under GSP conditionality.

These shifts echo a more general hardening of the EU's migration control focus in recent years. In sum, the EU's approach towards return and readmission has become increasingly based on a mix of informal

deals, first via positive conditionality via issue-linkages with other EU migration policies (such as visa and mobility partnerships) and non-migration policies (such as trade and development), and, increasingly, coercive strategies based on negative conditionality. This development shows the pressure that EU member states exert to benefit from EU leverage in the pursuit of return and readmission objectives. At the same time, member states have not always been cooperative, and continue to follow unilateral strategies in their external migration policies.

Approaches of European states to enforced return and readmission

While a multitude of actors make up Europe's deportation regime, states have the prerogative to regulate and control the access to asylum and the return of illegalized migrants. Since the 1990s, the issue of return has been a top priority on political agendas across Europe (Trauner 2018). Consequently, many governments in Europe have publicly declared the alleged need to control access to European territory and to return illegalized migrants to their countries of citizenship. To this end, they stressed the need for international cooperation and for closing the aforementioned readmission agreements. The call for more agreements, however, disregards that even states with higher numbers of these agreements have not substantially increased their return rates over time (Stutz & Trauner, 2022, Leerkes et al. 2022). Irrespectively, we have, by and large, witnessed a unified public *position* of European states on return: stressing the importance of returning migrants and increasing international cooperation to do so. By contrast, academic literature signals substantial variation regarding the *approaches to how* European states enforce the return of illegalized migrants.

Leerkes and Van Houte (2020, p. 321) have put forward a typology of “post-arrival migration enforcement regimes” that allows them to capture different approaches of how European states deal with the issue of return in practice. As the first defining feature of an enforcement regime, the authors distinguish *enforcement interests*, which depend on whether the return of illegalized migrants is only a desired public statement or also bears advantages for liberal states in practice by meeting their demand for security, rule of law, and economic growth (ibid.). Thereby, coercive measures and the forceful return of illegalized migrants can particularly be opposed to the human rights-based approach of migration governance or weaken economic sectors that are benefiting from illegalized migrants. The second feature, *enforcement capacities* are defined as the set of policies and agreements as well as the necessary structures needed to implement these policies (ibid.). In the field of return, these capacities mostly refer to the existence of readmission agreements with host- and transit countries, structures, and incentives to foster the “voluntary” return of migrants, as well as detention facilities or other means that allow the forceful return of migrants (ibid.). In the following sections, we will detail the post-arrival regimes of four European states—Italy, Switzerland, Germany, and Poland—by discussing their enforcement interests and enforcement capacities.

Italy: between international cooperation and domestic constraints

As a result of its geographical location, Italy is one of the main countries of entry for migrants coming to the EU and, consequently, often deemed to be responsible for examining asylum applications under the Dublin system. However, Italy is also a country of transit for migrants who aim to reach other European countries. Aiming to reduce the pressure on the Italian asylum system, the country has

undertaken great efforts to close readmission agreements with third countries. According to the *Inventory of Bilateral Agreements linked to Readmission*, Italy has managed to close 83 such agreements (Cassarino n.d.). Thereof, 38 have been closed with other European countries, 18 with countries from the Middle East or Northern Africa, 18 with other African countries, 2 with Latin American countries, and 7 with Asian countries (ibid.).

Nevertheless, Italy was considered to have both weak enforcement interests and limited enforcement capacities and is thus an example of a European state having a *thin enforcement regime* (Leerkes & Van Houte 2020). This categorization is mainly based on the view that the Italian government's will to return people lacking legal rights to stay may be considered to be severely limited by the economic demand for cheap workforce in the informal economic sector (ibid.). Furthermore, its enforcement capacities were considered weak since programs targeted at the “voluntary” return face constraints by rather narrow scope and budget as well as bureaucratic hurdles (Marino et al. 2022). Besides Italy, Spain is another country that is likewise strongly affected by illegalized migration but nevertheless has been classified as having only a thin enforcement regime (Leerkes & Van Houte 2020).

Italy's high number of readmission agreements shows that the issue of return has been a top priority for the Italian government for several decades. In the domestic arena, the demand for increasing the numbers of returns has mostly been driven by the political right that has been supported by anti-refugee activists on the streets and other forms of extra-parliamentary activities (Caselli et al. 2022). However, Italy's unilateral actions on return have also been under critical scrutiny by other European states and international institutions. This became apparent as Italy returned illegalized migrants from Italy to Libya between October 2004 and March 2006 and the European Parliament (EU), the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) as well as the United Nations' Human Rights Committee (CCPR) criticized human rights violations (Andrijasevic 2010). Thereby, the Italian media took a somewhat ambiguous role by leading a humanitarian discourse and foregrounding the need to save lives in the Mediterranean Sea all whilst benefiting from and zooming into the spectacle of militarized borders (Musarò & Parmiggiani 2017). Furthermore, despite the government's political rhetoric of presenting return and readmission policies as the preferred solution towards illegalized migrants, Italy has granted larger numbers of regularisations than any other EU country (Ambrosini 2012). Overall, despite being a top priority on the political agenda in Italy, the will to return people is substantially constrained by political demand and the human rights discourse as well as economic demands of the informal sector and the will to secure growth in the Italian economy.

The instability of the Italian party system as well as numerous changes of governments have hindered the establishment of a coherent migration policy (Gianfreda 2018). This is also the case for Italy's “voluntary” return program, which is funded by the EU and compared to programs in other European states rather new as it was founded less than two decades ago (Caselli et al., 2022). Until recently, these were run by non-profit organizations that followed a migrant-centered approach in return counselling, whereas the decision was taken by the *Prefettura* (Marino et al. 2022). The rate of “voluntary” returns in Italy fluctuates strongly and is consistently lower than the one in many other European states (Caselli et al., 2022). In contrast to these rather recent programs, Italy has built a large network of readmission agreements with home and transit countries over the course of several decades (Cassarino n.d.). Thereby, Italy has particularly developed strong ties with North African countries that are based on economic incentives and migration control measures in order to return people there (Cuttitta 2010). Thereby, different forms of cooperation with these numbers show that operability, not formalization, has been the main priority for Italy (Cassarino 2010). However, in light

of the large number of readmission agreements, the number of returns remains relatively low (Stutz & Trauner 2022).

Switzerland: strong multilateralism and enforcement capacities

Switzerland can be viewed as an example of a European country having a *thick enforcement regime* because it has both high interests in returning illegalized migrants as well as high return capacities (Leerkes & Van Houte 2020). While Switzerland is not an EU member state, it does participate in the Common European Asylum System (CEAS), most notably through the application of the Dublin Regulation and its Schengen membership since 2008. Legally, Schengen membership obliges Switzerland as a non-EU country to ensure an effective system of return and monitoring forced returns (Röthlisberger 2014). The Swiss system of forceful returns essentially builds on a vast network of readmission agreements with transit and home countries within and outside of Europe. Besides Switzerland, Norway and the Netherlands are further European countries that can be considered as having a thick enforcement regime (ibid).

Since the 1990s, the issue of enforced return has already been high on the Swiss political agenda (Ruedin & Meyer 2014). The initiative on the deportation of non-Swiss citizens with criminal records (*Ausschaffungsinitiative*) that has been accepted by 52.9% of the Swiss electorate in 2010 is an example of the high level of politicization of immigration and the issue of return (Bader & Probst 2018). Thereby, the right-wing Swiss People's Party, being the biggest party in Switzerland for over two decades, can be considered the driving force behind the politicization of asylum and forced return (Mazzoleni 2022). While we can observe a high interest in the return of rejected asylum seekers and illegalized migrants in Switzerland, there is only little political opposition against attempts to step up the number of returned migrants. The main opposition against return can mostly be found outside of the conventional political spectrum and is mostly driven by NGOs or civil society (Ruedin & Meyer 2014). Yet, the focus of these oppositions on single deportation cases leads to an absence of a more general discussion on return policies. Moreover, the low legitimacy of unconventional protest forms that have taken place since the 1980s (Bader & Probst 2018) has only little resonance in a democratic system that bears a great number of formal participation forms.

In 1986, the Swiss authorities started the current return program, which is mainly based on individual return aid, return consultation points, and return programs for people with special needs (Käser & Schenker 2008). Thereby, inter-departmental cooperation in return practices and inter-state cooperation have both been crucial for building and developing the Swiss return system (Perroulaz 2008). Yet even though the programs on "voluntary return" generated comparably high numbers of returns in the 1990s, forced returns have mostly outnumbered assisted returns since 2002 (Bader & Probst 2018). Switzerland has established a large set of coercive removal measures, including policies that allow the authorities to keep adults in pre-departure detention for up to 18 months and minors between 15 and 18 in detention for up to 12 months (Romer et al. 2022). The Swiss authorities distinguish between four different levels of coerciveness in return flights, including the possibility of a *special flight* during which several police officers are present, and the returnee is fully immobilized (State Secretariat for Migration 2024). During such deportation flights also representatives of an NGO are present that monitor the return and the safety of the person being returned (Röthlisberger 2014).

The Swiss system of forceful returns essentially builds on a vast network of readmission agreements with transit and home countries within and outside of Europe. The *Inventory of the Bilateral Agreements Linked to Readmission* counts a total of 72 bilateral agreements linked to readmission for Switzerland (Cassarino n.d.). According to this inventory, the Swiss authorities have concluded

readmission agreements with 39 states in Europe, 4 states in the Middle East and North African countries, 14 states in other African regions, 1 state in Latin America, and 14 states in Asia (ibid.). Thereby, the Swiss authorities have particularly moved from more formal readmission agreements to informal agreements and negotiated broader package deals and increasingly favored promoting and closing Migration Partnerships and Memorandum of Understanding. In 2009, Switzerland appointed a Special Ambassador for International Cooperation on Migration, aiming to increase its engagement in bilateral and regional cooperation on migration as well as to strengthen its position in international networks and fora. To this end, Switzerland is promoting multilateralism by hosting international forums on migration such as the Global Forum on Migration and Development and has been active in setting up international initiatives such as the UN High Level Dialogues on International Migration and Development (Babel et al. 2015).

Germany: from a targeted to a thick enforcement regime?

Germany has been perceived as a state having a *targeted enforcement regime* that has comparably high enforcement capacities but limited enforcement interests (Leerkes & Van Houte 2020). Whereas German authorities selectively deport some categories of rejected asylum seekers they are providing a *Duldung* (which is not a legal residence title or a right to stay but a formal toleration and temporary suspension of the deportation) to others (Jonitz & Leerkes 2022, Schütze 2022). Against the backdrop of rising numbers of asylum seekers and refugees as well as political pressure for a more restrictive asylum policy, the German government could be perceived to shift towards a thick enforcement regime. Over the past few decades, Germany has built a large network aiming to increase the number of “voluntary” returns, but the country has been somewhat reluctant to use coercive measures and forced returns. According to the *Inventory of the Bilateral Agreements Linked to Readmission* by Cassarino (2022), Germany has closed 51 bilateral readmission agreements. Out of these, 39 agreements have been closed with other European countries, 5 with countries in the Middle East or North Africa and 7 with Asian countries (ibid). Notably, Germany has not closed any agreements with a country from Sub-Saharan Africa. Besides Germany, Sweden is another country that has traditionally been categorized as having relatively strong enforcement capacities but preferred to use these in a rather selective way in the past (Leerkes & Van Houte 2020).

The limited will to enforce return decisions in Germany is not mainly caused by an absence of legal measures but by difficulties in implementing them and opposition against coercive measures (Ellermann 2006, Kreienbrink 2007). Germany has also been known for its openness towards people seeking protection during the 2015 refugee protection crisis (Ostrand 2015). In recent years, however, the country has witnessed the rise of the far right-wing party *Alternative für Deutschland* (AfD) which is based on an anti-immigration and pro-remigration rhetoric and perceives immigration as an economic and cultural threat (Berbuir et al. 2015). Yet, also political parties of the broader political spectrum such as the opposition leader Friedrich Merz from the Christian Democratic Union (CDU) have called for more restrictions on the rights of rejected asylum seekers (Eydlin 2023). His demands to restrict access for rejected asylum seekers to some services of the health system for up to 18 months have been embedded in more general discourses on the abuse of asylum and the welfare system. Thereby, pro-refugee organizations appeared to be unable to strategically engage with these dominant frames (Fadaee 2021). Ultimately, these shifts in the public and political debate in Germany could not only lead to a change in the tone of discourses or diminish the rights of rejected asylum seekers but also increase the demand to return people lacking the legal documents to stay.

Since the 1970s, Germany has built up structures and networks that aim to return illegalized migrants but prioritized “voluntary” return over coercive measures and forced returns most of the time. The first “voluntary return” program (“Return of Talents”) that was set up in 1974 has particularly tried to provide a positive view on returnees and framed the return as an opportunity for both returnees and their home countries (Caselli et al. 2022). Since that time, Germany has built an extensive network of counselling centers across the country that aim to incentivize people to return and prevent the state from making use of coercive measures (ibid.). Yet, several factors such as the insecure financial support of return counselling centers, substantial regional variations in the density of such centers as well as the large number of actors involved in these programs have severely limited such programs (Grote 2015). The lack of centralization of responsibilities to more specialized authorities appear to have particularly limited the numbers of returns through “voluntary” return programs (Kreienbrink 2007).

Overall, the limited use of forced return in the past is rather based on a reluctance to use coercive measures in the law than in the absence of such possibilities in the law. For example, Germany could hold people in pre-removal detention for up to 18 months according to its legal regulation, such detentions, however, usually last less than one month and rarely exceed 6 months in practice (Stiller & Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik 2022). As a consequence of the German reluctance to use such measures, there has been a decline in deportations between 1993 and 2013 (Ruedin & Meyer 2014). Since 2018, however, the number of deportations has outnumbered the number of voluntary returns (Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung 2023, Federal Office for Migration and Refugees 2024). Furthermore, the current Social Democratic chancellor Olaf Scholz has announced that Germany must toughen up on asylum and drastically increase the number of forced returns from Germany (Hickmann & Kurbjuweit 2023).

Poland: differential approaches towards return from the territory and border

Poland formally accessed the European Union in 2004, through which it became part of the Common European Asylum System and, due to its geographical position, formed the EU's external border. In the accession period, the extension of the EU *acquis* on immigration and asylum matters has been controversial for Eastern European countries, including Poland. They criticized the EU's unilateral approach to determining the conditions of their partnership, which came to the fore amongst others when negotiating the “safe third country rule” and readmission agreements (Lavenex 1998). Eastern European countries realized that asylum and immigration policies were “instrumentalized by EU Member States in order to establish a filter or a buffer zone between them and the countries of emigration” (Lavenex 1998, p. 290, Collinson 1996, Vermeersch 2005). This caused difficulties, for example in maintaining traditional and economic bonds with neighboring non-EU countries, for whom Poland now had to introduce visas.

Present day, Poland plays a “triple role” when it comes to migration and mobility in the European Union. First of all, Poland is and has long been a country of emigration, with intensive outward mobility of Polish citizens for purposes of labor migration. Poland is also a country of immigration, notably since the 1990s. The gradual opening up of the county also ensured that anti-immigrant views first started to surface (Krzyżanowski 2018). This continued the decades after, peaking in the second half of 2015 with the then-ruling radical right *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* (PiS) party heavily politicizing migration in a racialized manner. As a country of immigration, Poland recruits dazzling numbers of temporary foreign workers to keep the Polish economy running (Szulecka et al. 2018). Poland is also a country of destination for Belarusian citizens fleeing the Lukashenko regime and Ukrainians fleeing Russia's invasion since 2014 (Duszczuk & Kaczmarczyk 2022). Poland is similarly receiving many Polish returning

migrants. These include Polish citizens being deported from other EU member states, who according to Klajn (2023) mostly comprise “undesirable migrants”: Poles deemed criminals or otherwise a threat. Klaus (2023) details how these deportations are absent from Polish national discourse as deportation is associated with stigma and failure, especially if serving a prison sentence has been part of the deportation trajectory. White (2014) however shows that the return of Polish nationals is also desirable for Poland, due to gaps in the labor market, an aging population, and a shortage of workers. Poland has a long history of repatriation schemes for Polish nationals (Lesińska 2013), such as through the *Return Program* initiated by the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy in 2007. In these schemes, return from Poles abroad constitutes a symbolic affirmation of Polish collective identity and willingness to contribute to one's country of origin. Third, after Poland acceded to the EU and the Schengen zone, its position as a country of “transit” also solidified. While being a country of first arrival in the EU, not everyone who reaches Poland stays. Many decide to leave Poland and move on to other EU countries, with Poland also turning a blind eye to such secondary movements (Klaus 2023, Klaus & Szulecka 2023). Our review indeed shows that Poland's interests and capacity in enforcing migration control are primarily geared towards fortifying the EU's external border, with only differential interests and capacity given to enforcing returns.

Indeed, border enforcement is at the core of Polish interests in controlling migration and has been so for a long time (Alscher 2017, Szulecka 2019, Klaus 2023). Due to its geographical location at the external border of the EU, they share similarities with the EU's southern Member States, whose main priority likewise lies with controlling their borders (Leerkes & van Houte 2020). At the time Europe was debating EU-wide solidarity mechanisms in 2015, the Polish government privileged public support towards border guards at Poland's eastern border, as opposed to serving their equal share in receiving refugees (Goździak & Main 2020). This response should be understood in a wider post-2015 ‘hostile environment’ in the country, where the national PiS government actively polarized society about migration and displacement. Most prominent in both academic and political debates have been the pushbacks Poland enforces at the Polish-Belarusian border, which helps to align their imperative to fortify the EU's external border with PiS dominant “security discourse” (Krzyżanowski 2018). In an opaque and discretionary process, Polish authorities have only selectively allowed asylum seekers into Poland for their applications to be processed, whereas the vast majority were forcefully returned to Belarus (Szczepanik 2018). Polish and Belarusian human rights activists have taken this case to the European Court of Human Rights, who have condemned the Polish government for these practices. The Polish government however continues to block asylum seekers from entering Poland at the Terespol crossing to date (Klaus 2018). Various authors (Klaus 2023, Klaus & Szulecka 2023) have noted the profound differences in the Polish approach towards asylum seekers at the Belarusian border and asylum seekers from Eastern Europe and argued that racism and xenophobia lie at its core. Poland's approach towards Belarusian and Ukrainian refugees was strikingly more open, which signals that deterrence as a policy tool is therefore “applied only towards certain groups, mainly people of color and non-Christians, especially Muslims” (Klaus & Szulecka 2023, 468). The little academic research on enforced return in Poland signals that further interior enforcement has low priorities, both when it comes to accepting “secondary movements” as well as apprehending illegalized migrants (Klaus 2023).

Due to this emphasis on both border control and the relatively low numbers of illegalized migrants in the country (EMN 2015), Klaus (2023) argues that Poland did not develop elaborate deportation policies. Poland currently only has 6 bilateral readmission agreements with countries in Central-Eastern Europe and Asia, and three more are being negotiated (Cassarino n.d.). While this might lead us to think that Poland has a weak return enforcement capacity, statistics on return seem to signal differently: in 2019, 96% of all return orders issued were enforced. This picture becomes a bit more

complicated, however, when we zoom in on the situation on the ground. Klaus and Szulecka (2023) show that the vast majority of the return orders issued (up to 80%) are given to Ukrainian citizens, who for the most part leave the country in a voluntary and non-assisted way. After overstaying their visa, these Ukrainians travel back to Ukraine independently and only then become interrupted by Polish border guards. Upon discovering their illegalized status, these border guards consequently issue a return decision which is then immediately executed without the necessity for them to use coercion (see also Szulecka 2019). The remaining illegalized migrants who do not plan to leave Poland often manage to stay out of sight of authorities (Klaus 2023). Szulecka (2019) details that the 2008 Return Directive was transposed into Polish national law in 2013, which introduced a new procedure for issuing a return order. Together with a specified timeframe during which return needs to take place, Polish border guards took over the mandate from the Office for Foreigners to issue a return order to rejected asylum seekers, and now became responsible for issuing all orders. Limited research available on Poland's enforcement structure shows that detention is an often-used measure. Similar to other EU countries, these detention centers are located close to the border and serve to prepare deportation trajectories administratively, legally, and physically. While this practice is criticized by societal organizations in the country, border guards maintain that it is of key importance to execute return orders - both for purposes of identifying illegalized migrants and physically keeping them present until deportation takes place. A border guard in Szulecka's (2019, p. 62) study further mentioned that there are "no financial or technical problems in organizing forced returns".

NGOs in Europe: between collaboration and contestation of Europe's deportation regime

Civil society, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) by extension (hereafter, NGOs), are a heterogeneous group that play multiple, sometimes overlapping and sometimes conflicting, roles in the European deportation regime. There is an emerging body of scholarship documenting the role of civil society actors in migration and border governance, highlighting their relationships to supra- and intergovernmental organizations, as well as the logics, practices and rationalities that inform interactions between humanitarian NGOs and border control efforts (Cuttitta et al. 2023). We touch upon both of these debates here when discussing the involvement of civil society actors in the implementation of assisted voluntary return (AVR) policies and programs in Europe (Kalir & Wissink 2016, Kalir 2017, McGhee 2016, Vandevordt 2017). Afterwards, we will discuss a third area of emerging research (Cuttitta et al. 2023), namely those that details the emergence of activist groups and organizations that develop radical political positions and foster new patterns of solidarity – most notably for our case, in anti-deportation protests (Rosenberger et al. 2018). Below, we will first detail NGO involvement in AVR, before discussing protests and activist practices within the wider European deportation regime.

Despite being born out of a humanitarian tradition assisting displaced persons after WWII (Vandevordt 2017), AVR programs nowadays consist of a "state induced-return program" (Marino et al. 2023) that offers migrants return counselling as well as logistical and financial "assistance" for their return "home". It is often framed as the result of migrants' "voluntary choice" (Black et al. 2011) and a durable solution for migrants without the right to residency (Bendixsen 2020). While the exact set-up

and relationships between actors involved in AVR differ from country to country (see Marino et al. 2023), small-scale NGOs often cooperate with IOM and rely on the EC's Asylum, Migration, and Integration (AMIF) fund, to assume tasks in the implementation of enforced return policies that governments themselves are unwilling or unable to fulfil. Notably, governments have limited capacity and credentials to "persuade" illegalized migrants to return "voluntarily", which has long been identified as a major obstacle in their efforts to remove them (Black et al. 2004). It is often NGOs who foster illegalized migrants' trust in the AVR system, disseminate information to them, help to obtain documents and reduce the stigma associated with return (Black et al. 2011). They do so primarily through providing "return counselling" (Cleton & Schweitzer 2021) to rejected asylum seekers and other illegalized migrants. In it, their humanitarian identity distinguishes their approach to AVR from that of states, as the well-being of migrants is their primary motivation as opposed to governing migration (Kalir 2017, Crane & Lawson 2020, Schweitzer 2022). Yet, whether AVR is truly humanitarian is contested, particularly considering the political legitimization it serves, underlying ideological foundation and funding opportunities humanitarian projects potentially bring.

Indeed, critical migration and border scholars hold that AVR and deportation are part and parcel of the same humanitarian border enforcement policy that relies on the intertwinement of care and control (Bendixsen 2020, Marino et al. 2023). The same, so they argue, goes for the actors involved in these seemingly separate procedures. Kalir & Wissink (2016) argue that NGOs in the Netherlands are part of a wider "deportation continuum" in which state and non-state actors converge, work together, and share similar terminology and categories, underlying views on borders, citizenship, and rights, as well as their handling face-to-face interactions. Precisely because NGO workers are not backing any anti-migration or ill-intended policies – none want to cooperate on deportations – Kalir (2017) argues that the underlying ideology has become pervasive and serves to legitimate both AVR and deportation. He argues that "a critical interrogation of AVR reveals how hegemonic ideas about free choice, state sovereignty, and territoriality, which are invested in notions of "voluntarism" and "home", eloquently succeed in concealing the violence that is implied in using them for promoting AVR [...] (ibid., 57)". So, since AVR programs are based on the same logic that champions state sovereignty in justifying forced removals, some argue for using the term "soft deportation" to reference such programs (Kalir 2017, Leerkes et al. 2017). In a similar way, Crane and Lawson (2020) argue that humanitarian organizations that provide return counseling in Belgium, Germany, and the UK, solely display "minor acts of care" that help to alleviate hardships of individual migrants. While this allows for a more humane and compassionate space to navigate return, it at the same time does not substantially change the overall restrictive situation at hand, which will eventually accumulate in exclusion.

Others hold that NGOs are not merely reinforcing this overall restrictive and oppressive deportation regime. Even within it, Schweitzer (2022) argues that return counsellors from civil society make room for "voluntariness" by upholding ethical and procedural standards and by remaining independent from the government. Important standards that he identified in his work in Austria and the UK relate to guaranteeing the absence of coercion, the availability of acceptable alternatives, and providing access to adequate information. Case study research has identified that organizations' ideological orientation, relative independence from the government and their categorization of potential returnees (Cleton & Schweitzer 2021, McGhee et al. 2016) are crucial for understanding how they approach return counselling. Centering the Belgian case, Vandevoordt (2017) details that civil society actors are allowed to fulfil their job according to their own values, even if they began to function more within a wider government strategy of expelling illegalized migrants. He argues that the Belgian context and legal-political system made NGOs "immune" against values, practices and norms through which nation-states operate, effectively allowing them to implement state policies without changing their own

values and practices. However, Kox & Staring (2022) show that the gradual inclusion of humanitarian support organizations into their migration control policies has led to a decrease in the number of these organizations, a reduction of their independence and an increased focus on selection and return. Their ethnographic research among illegalized migrants in the Netherlands shows the consequences of this move: they experience exclusion, selection, and enforcement by humanitarian organizations and therefore doubt whether they are to be trusted. They situate this development in a wider, European development where humanitarian organizations are either co-opted or criminalized (see also Cuttitta et al. 2023). They argue that there are severe consequences to these strategies: illegalized migrants will further withdraw and turn away from this type of assistance altogether.

As became clear in the paragraphs above, NGOs are heavily involved in state-funded AVR policies and programs. While some abide by underlying state logics of deterrence and exclusion, others use their existing room for manoeuvre in delivering counselling and services to make room for "voluntariness". Some NGOs can effectively act as both "insiders" and "outsiders": working with the government on AVR, while at the same time campaigning against certain aspects of the overall restrictive regime (McGhee et al. 2016). This is indeed another important role that NGOs in the European deportation regime play: they are involved in anti-deportation protests. Even though deportation is core to the state's means to control mobility, it has long been a non-issue in public discourse (Ruedin & Meier 2014). By challenging the state's legitimate means to deport, protests mobilized by NGOs might have a political agenda-setting effect that pressures politicians into a response. Research by Ruedin and Meier (2014) indeed shows that in Austria, Germany and Switzerland, NGOs and churches play a crucial role in politicizing deportation and leading protest actions. Statham and Geddes (2006) argue that NGOs have an important role through discursive action, alliance building and their agenda-setting power. They actively voice and propagate concerns with state policy that are latently present in the wider citizenry, to add frames to the discursive opportunity structure. Freedman (2011) at the same time argues that NGOs act as a form of "gatekeepers" who provide ambivalent support to rejected asylum seekers in their claims-making. Discussing the case of France, she argues that fragmentation in the sector, limited funding and government dependence have resulted in some NGOs not being able to criticize the government, instead going along with the dominant narrative.

The literature that discusses the involvement of NGOs in anti-deportation activism distils two strategies. The first reflects what Freedman (2011) described as "pragmatic activism", meaning that the primary source of motivation is a "humanitarian", personal concern based on everyday contact and driven by personal sentiments, as opposed to a wider claim of moral injustice or political criticism of migration control. Anti-deportation protests by protest movements and NGOs documented in the literature indeed challenge the state's legitimate right to deport mostly on an individual basis, by focusing on individuals with high levels of societal integration (Bader & Probst 2018, Rosenberger & Winkler 2014). They argue that these individuals have a legitimate right to be exempted from the threat of deportation due to the intricate link between themselves and the society they live in, irrespective of formal membership status. Wittock and colleagues (2021) note this in the case of the Netherlands and Belgium, where anti-deportation protests for illegalized migrant children and their families have been at the center of NGO-led politicization and protest, and in both countries resulted in policy change. To the contrary, Vandevordt and Verschragen (2019) note that pro-refugee social movements engage in what they call "subversive humanitarianism", that go against the dominant terms of exclusion. By reframing individual claims into wider human rights issues, such protests open up space for political agency and contestations against hegemonic perceptions of deservingness and citizenship. Protests that challenge the legitimacy of deportation as such are much rarer but include

campaigns for the collective regularization of illegalized migrants (Chimienti 2013) and efforts to disrupt attempted deportations (Hinger et al. 2018).

Conclusion

This working paper presented a non-exhaustive review of the literature on the European deportation regime, focusing specifically on converging and diverging positionings on enforced returns. We thereby centered a selection of the actors that together shape this regime: IOM, UNHCR, the EU, four European states and several NGOs. Following the regime literature in the social sciences widely, the paper shows the multiplicity of positions of these different actors working and shaping the practice and discourse on enforced returns on a day-to-day basis. We wrote the review along two common denominators in regime literature, namely that of complexities and complementarities between actors, as well as the norms and discourse that informs their work, and that they shape in turn.

The review shows that on the most basic level, almost all actors converge in their basic *views* on borders and citizenship. They all accept that sovereign states have the legitimate right to determine who can be rightfully part of their citizenry and who cannot – and therefore, who can be expelled. This might be obvious for European states but similarly counts for international organizations and a big part of the NGOs. Our review indeed shows that IOM and UNHCR, both heavily dependent on voluntary donations from a handful of Western states, are at best ambivalent about the topic of enforced return. Nowadays, both play an important role in the implementation and operational aspects of return, assist during reintegration, and facilitate inter-state cooperation on readmission. For the NGOs too, we see that a substantial part of them (implicitly) accept that enforced return is a feature of our modern world and play a part in it, by operating assisted voluntary return programs. There is considerable difference among this group of NGOs, however, in whether they try to keep distance from the deporting state and provide legal assistance to challenge return orders, for example. Research that documented the activities and strategies of NGOs involved in protest similarly shows that very few of them engage in strategies that reject the overall right of states to exclude non-citizens and limit themselves to protesting specific (often deserving) cases only. As Hinger and colleagues (2018) detail, this leads to missed opportunities to question the fundamental rightness of enforced return in political discussions.

In terms of norms and discourse, there seems to be a clear intertwining between securitization and humanitarianism on stances to enforced return – yet that the degree to which this is the case, and the way in which it manifest, differs from actor to actor. At the EU level, studies show convincingly that enforced return has been heavily securitized – like migration overall – with the EU making the “fight against illegal migration” a policy priority for the past 30 years. In different EU member states, this securitizing discourse is also permanent, yet in differentiated ways. In Poland, for example, securitization takes an explicitly racialized character when it comes to removals and pushbacks whereas, in Italy, the alleged benefit of illegalized migrant labor supersedes a clear securitizing discourse. For the work of IOM, UNHCR and NGOs involved in AVR in particular, however, we see a clearer intertwining of the two. Studies show that these actors do not simply follow this overly securitized, state narrative, but try to balance their own (human rights) tradition and concerns for the welfare of illegalized migrants with donor demands. Much in line with Aradau’s (2004) work on human trafficking, however, literature shows that this “humanitarian concern” for the needs and wellbeing of illegalized migrants and their *insecure* status can be appropriated within this overall restrictive framework. As a result, humanitarianism, just like securitization, sustains “practical interventions with

the purpose of managing the phenomenon of [return]" (Aradau 2004, 253). In terms of *approach* towards enforced returns, finally, there similarly is variety. At the EU level, we see a clear convergence towards harmonizing return and readmission policy, with measures taken since the 1990s to include standard readmission clauses in trade agreements, and creating linkages between development policy, visa, and cooperation on enforced returns. When we zoom in on approaches in different member states, however, we see that both interest and enforcement capacities differ from country to country. Reasons for this differential approach vary from geography to historical connections and the demand for labor in informal economies. Our review, concluding, thus shows that Europe's deportation regime is indeed continuously "in the making", fitting together different actors, practices, discourses, that converge, oppose and adapt over time. For the years to come, we expect that the pervasive emphasis at the EU level to secure illegalized migration and widening mandate of Frontex as the EU's operational organization for all enforced return, will likely only further spur such polycentrism among deportation regime actors.

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